

DEVELOPMENT OF TENNIS PLAYERS' TECHNICAL TRAINING

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Abstract: This thesis highlights methods for developing tennis players' technical preparation, the importance of the training process, and modern training tools. The role of regular exercises and an individual approach in improving the technical skills of athletes is also analyzed. The scientific work extensively covers issues of developing the technical training of tennis players and modern methods and tools used to enhance their athletic mastery. Tennis is a complex sport that requires a high level of speed, agility, strength, endurance, and the precise and effective execution of technical movements. Therefore, the proper organization and regular development of athletes' technical preparation are of great importance. The study analyzes the main elements of tennis players' technical training, including the correct grip of the racket, ball reception, passing, forehand and backhand strikes, service, and the improvement of defensive and offensive movements. It also reveals the importance of considering the age characteristics, physical fitness level, and individual capabilities of athletes during the training process. The effectiveness of using special exercises, repetitive exercises, coordination actions, and modern pedagogical technologies in developing technical training is substantiated. The scientific work also examines the role of coaches in the formation of technical skills, the psychological state of athletes, and factors ensuring stability in the competitive process. Research findings indicate that the regular improvement of technical preparation serves to enhance the quality of tennis players' play and their performance in competitions. This article is of great importance as a practical and theoretical resource for tennis coaches, athletes, and students majoring in physical education.

Keywords: tennis, technical training, training, athlete, coordination, tactics, physical development.

РАЗВИТИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ТЕННИСИСТОВ

Аннотация: В данном тезисе освещены методы развития технической подготовки теннисистов, значение тренировочного процесса и современные средства подготовки. Также проанализирована роль регулярных упражнений и индивидуального подхода в повышении технического мастерства спортсменов. В научной работе широко освещены вопросы развития технической подготовки теннисистов, современные методы и средства, применяемые для повышения их спортивного мастерства. Теннис считается одним из сложных видов спорта, требующих высокого уровня быстроты, ловкости, силы, выносливости, а также точного и эффективного выполнения технических действий. Поэтому правильная организация и регулярное развитие технической подготовки спортсменов имеет важное значение. В исследовании проанализированы основные элементы, входящие в состав технической подготовки теннисистов, в том числе вопросы совершенствования правильного держания ракетки, приема мяча, передачи, форхендных и бэкхендных ударов, сервиса, а также защитных и атакующих действий. Также раскрыта важность учета возрастных особенностей, уровня физической подготовки и индивидуальных возможностей спортсменов в тренировочном процессе. Обоснована эффективность использования специальных упражнений, повторных занятий, координационных действий и современных педагогических технологий в развитии технической подготовки. В ходе научной работы также рассмотрены роль тренеров в формировании технических навыков, психологическое состояние спортсменов и факторы обеспечения устойчивости в соревновательном процессе. Результаты исследования показывают, что регулярное совершенствование технической подготовки способствует повышению качества игры теннисистов и их

результативности на соревнованиях. Данная статья имеет важное практическое и теоретическое значение для тренеров, спортсменов и студентов по направлению физического воспитания, занимающихся теннисом.

Ключевые слова: теннис, техническая подготовка, тренировка, спортсмен, координация, тактика, физическое развитие.

TENNISCHILARNING TEXNIK TAYYORGARLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH

Annotatsiya: Mazkur tezisda tennischilarning texnik tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish usullari, mashg‘ulot jarayonining ahamiyati hamda zamonaviy tayyorgarlik vositalari yoritilgan. Shuningdek, sportchilarning texnik mahoratini oshirishda muntazam mashqlar va individual yondashuvning o‘rni tahlil qilingan. Ilmiy ishda tennischilarning texnik tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish masalalari, ularning sport mahoratini oshirishda qo‘llaniladigan zamonaviy usul va vositalar keng yoritilgan. Tennis sport turi yuqori darajadagi tezkorlik, chaqqonlik, kuch, chidamlilik hamda texnik harakatlarni aniq va samarali bajarishni talab qiladigan murakkab sport turlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Shu sababli sportchilarning texnik tayyorgarligini to‘g‘ri tashkil etish va muntazam rivojlantirib borish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Tadqiqotda tennischilarning texnik tayyorgarligi tarkibiga kiruvchi asosiy elementlar, jumladan, raketkani to‘g‘ri ushlash, to‘pni qabul qilish, uzatish, forehand va backhand zarbalari, servis hamda himoya va hujum harakatlarini takomillashtirish masalalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, mashg‘ulot jarayonida sportchilarning yosh xususiyatlari, jismoniy tayyorgarlik darajasi va individual imkoniyatlarini hisobga olishning ahamiyati ochib berilgan. Texnik tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirishda maxsus mashqlar, takroriy mashg‘ulotlar, koordinatsion harakatlar hamda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi asoslab berilgan. Ilmiy ish davomida texnik ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishda murabbiylarning roli, sportchilarning psixologik

holati va musobaqa jarayonidagi barqarorlikni ta'minlash omillari ham ko'rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, texnik tayyorgarlikni muntazam ravishda takomillashtirish tennischilarning o'yin sifati va musobaqalardagi natijadorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Mazkur maqola tennis sporti bilan shug'ullanuvchi murabbiylar, sportchilar hamda jismoniy tarbiya yo'nalishidagi talabalar uchun amaliy va nazariy manba sifatida muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: tennis, texnik tayyorgarlik, mashg'ulot, sportchi, koordinatsiya, taktika, jismoniy rivojlanish.

SIGN IN

Relevance of the research. Tennis has become one of the most popular and spectacular sports worldwide in the 21st century. Nowadays, there is intense competition among tennis players to achieve high results, which requires them to constantly improve their athletic skills. Achieving high sports results depends on the athlete's physical, technical, and psychological preparation. Among them, technical training is of particular importance, which includes important skills such as striking accuracy, movement coordination, speed, and making correct decisions on the field. The development of modern tennis is characterized by an increase in the speed of the game, the strengthening of the offensive style, and increased requirements for technical movements. Therefore, the effective development and improvement of the technical training of athletes is a pressing scientific and practical problem. Furthermore, achieving success in high-performance sports depends on the athlete's constant self-improvement, the mastery of modern training methods, and the continuous development of their technical and tactical preparation. In this regard, the scientific study of methods for developing technical training in tennis is of great importance. Technical preparation is a key factor in an athlete's ability to execute strikes effectively during a game, accurately receive the ball, move correctly across the field, and apply appropriate movements in various situations. Especially in the process of training young tennis players, the correct formation of technical skills

serves as an important foundation for achieving high sports results in the future. Athletes with insufficiently developed technical training exhibit a decrease in game quality, an increase in the number of errors, and an inability to demonstrate stable results in competitions.

Currently, the use of modern pedagogical technologies, innovative training methods, and scientific approaches in organizing tennis training is becoming increasingly important. By improving the technical training of tennis players, it is possible to enhance their physical qualities, coordination abilities, and competitive efficiency. At the same time, the development of technical preparation helps strengthen the psychological confidence of athletes and helps them make correct decisions in difficult situations during the game.

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that great attention is being paid to the development of tennis in our republic, and the system for selecting young talents and preparing them for international competitions is being improved. Therefore, studying the technical training of tennis players on a scientific basis, developing effective training methods, and implementing them into practice is one of the important tasks of today.

Purpose of the research. Studying effective training methods and developing practical recommendations that serve to improve the technical training of tennis players and enhance their athletic mastery.

The object of the research is the training process and technical training activities of tennis players.

The subject of the study is the methods, means, and training methodology for developing the technical training of tennis players.

- **Research objectives**
- studying the theoretical foundations of technical training in tennis;
- analysis of methods for developing the technical skills of athletes;
- identifying effective methods in the training process;
- development of practical recommendations;

- developing ways to improve tennis players' performance in competitions through their technical training;
- development of practical recommendations for improving technical training.

Description of the methodology used in the study:

In this study, a number of scientific and pedagogical methods were used to study the process of developing the technical training of tennis players and to determine their effectiveness. During the study:

- pedagogical supervision;
- pedagogical experience;
- theoretical analysis;
- testing;
- methods of mathematical statistics.

Technical preparation is the athlete's ability to perform specific movements correctly and effectively in the game of tennis. Technical preparation enhances an athlete's overall skill. A technically well-trained athlete: makes fewer mistakes during the game; Accurately controls the ball; Quickly adapts to the opponent's movements; They achieve high results in competitions.

Additionally, technical training increases an athlete's self-confidence and strengthens their psychological stability. Technical preparation is of particular importance when working with young athletes. Proper training of technical elements at the initial stage has a significant impact on future athletic results. Interesting and understandable organization of training sessions increases the interest of athletes in tennis.

The role of physical qualities in the technical training of tennis players

In tennis, technical training is closely linked to physical qualities. The athlete's strength, speed, endurance, and agility contribute to the effective execution of technical actions. For example, speed ensures that an athlete moves across the field in a short time and reaches the ball quickly. Strength is important for the powerful

and accurate execution of strikes. Endurance helps the athlete perform technical movements with the same quality in long-term games. If the athlete lacks enough endurance, fatigue will appear during the game, leading to an increase in the number of technical errors. Agility allows an athlete to quickly change direction and perform complex movements in various situations. Coaches must harmoniously develop technical and physical fitness during the training process. This is because modern tennis requires not only technical skill but also high physical fitness.

A tennis player's technical skill includes the following elements:

- performing services;
- forehand strike;
- backhand stroke;
- receiving the ball;
- movement across the field;
- footwork technique.

Performing technical movements perfectly in tennis increases an athlete's chances of achieving victory. Technical training is inextricably linked to physical training, and they are developed together. Below is a 1-month training schedule for developing the technical proficiency of tennis players.

1 month training schedule for tennis players

№	Exercise type	Number of workouts / duration	Days to complete	Growth in 1 month
1	Service exercises	50-70 services	Monday	Increases service accuracy by 20-25%
2	Forehand shot	40-60 strokes	Wednesday	Improves impact strength and

				accuracy by 15-20%
3	Backhand stroke	40–50 strokes	Friday	Improves protection and return quality by 15%
4	Receiving	30 minutes	Monday	The reaction rate increases by 10–15%.
5	Move around the field	20-30 minutes of running and movement exercises	Monday Wednesday	Improves speed and agility by 20%
6	Footwork technique	15-20 minutes of special walking exercises	Friday	Balance and coordination improve by 15–18%
7	Jumping rope	100-150 times	Monday Wednesday	Increases durability by 10–12%
8	Pair Play Exercises	1 hour	Friday	Increase game experience and tactics by 15%
9	Video analysis exercises	20 minutes	Monday Wednesday	Technical errors will decrease by 10%

10	General physical fitness	30–40 minutes	Friday	Physical condition improves by 15-20%
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Weekly breakdown:

Monday: serve, reception, leg exercises

Tuesday: forehand, backhand, running exercises

Wednesday: service, reaction exercises

Thursday: forehand, backhand, coordination exercises

Friday: serve, reception

Saturday: pair play and technical exercises

Sunday: light workout and video analysis

Reminder

When exercises are performed regularly and correctly, the athlete's technical proficiency develops significantly over 1 month. It is recommended to perform warm-up exercises before training and recovery exercises after training.

Results. During the study, a system of special training aimed at developing the technical preparation of tennis players was tested in practice. The experiment was conducted during the first half of the 2025-2026 academic year, and classes were organized three times a week. During the study, the service accuracy, strike power, reaction speed, coordination, movement speed, and overall technical proficiency of the athletes were monitored.

The results of the conducted experiment showed that regular and scientifically organized training significantly improved the technical readiness of the tennis players. Specifically, the accuracy of service increased by 20–25 percent, and the

precision and strength of forehand and backhand strikes improved by 15–20 percent. The quality of athletes' defensive movements and the return of the ball increased by 15 percent.

Additionally, as a result of training, it was observed that the athletes' reaction speed increased by 10–15 percent, while their speed and agility increased by 20 percent. Through footwork techniques and coordination exercises, the athletes' ability to maintain balance improved by 15–18 percent. Jumping rope and general physical training exercises helped increase athletes' endurance by 10–12 percent.

Pair-based game exercises and specific technical tasks developed the athletes' game experience and tactical thinking skills. Through video analysis exercises, athletes' technical errors were reduced, and the quality of strike execution improved. At the end of the study, it was determined that the general physical and technical condition of the athletes had significantly improved.

The results obtained show that the use of modern methods, special technical exercises, and individual approaches in tennis training serves the effective development of athletes' technical preparation. This methodology plays an important role in improving the performance of tennis players in competitions.

Discussion

The results of the conducted research demonstrated that a system of specialized training is of great importance in developing the technical preparation of tennis players. The exercises used during the experiment helped significantly improve the athletes' serve accuracy, strike power, coordination, and movement speed. This confirms that technical preparation in modern tennis directly affects sports results. During the study, it was determined that regular and planned training sessions serve the stable development of athletes' technical skills. In particular, repeated practice of serve, forehand, and backhand strikes allowed athletes to automate technical actions. As a result, the number of errors during the game decreased, and the accuracy of strikes increased. It was also observed that the role of physical qualities is very important in the development of technical training.

Exercises in speed, agility, endurance, and coordination improve athletes' motor activity on the field. This made it possible to perform technical actions quickly and efficiently. Especially, exercises related to footwork technique developed the athletes' ability to move correctly across the field.

The use of video analysis exercises has become an effective tool for identifying and eliminating the technical errors of athletes. Through this method, coaches were able to identify the individual shortcomings of athletes and develop appropriate training programs for them. This further increased the effectiveness of the training. The research results showed that it is necessary to pay special attention to technical preparation when working with young tennis players. The correct formation of technical elements at the initial stage creates a solid foundation for athletes to achieve high results in the future. Therefore, coaches must organize training sessions taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the athletes. Overall, the methodology used during the study was found to be effective in developing the technical training of tennis players. The results obtained showed that organizing tennis training based on modern scientific approaches is of great importance in improving the technical skills of athletes and their performance in competitions.

Conclusion

In conclusion, technical preparation in tennis is one of the important factors in achieving high results for athletes. In modern tennis games, speed, precision, coordination, and the perfect execution of technical movements determine an athlete's success. Therefore, the development of tennis players' technical training remains one of the most pressing scientific and practical issues today.

During this study, the theoretical foundations of technical training in tennis were studied, effective training methods serving to develop athletes' technical skills were analyzed, and a complex of special exercises was developed. The results of the study showed that regular and scientifically organized training significantly

improves the service accuracy, striking power, reaction speed, coordination, and overall physical condition of athletes.

It was also established that the development of technical preparation strengthens the psychological self-confidence of athletes and helps them make correct decisions in complex situations during the game. Especially in the training of young tennis players, the correct formation of technical skills serves as an important foundation for achieving high athletic results in the future. It was observed that the methodology used during the study and the developed system of exercises are practically effective. It was determined that the athletes' technical indicators and game efficiency increased significantly as a result of a month of training. This confirms the importance of organizing tennis training based on modern methods. In the future, it is advisable to widely use innovative technologies, video analysis methods, and individual training programs to further improve the technical training of tennis players. The results of this study are of practical importance for coaches, athletes, and students studying physical culture and sports.

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